

Social Economic Analysis Of Women's Role In Informal Sector House (Case Study: Ibu Nyai , Babakan Lebak Village, Dramaga, West Java)

Amin Sadiqin

STIE Mahardhika Surabaya

email: aminsadiqin@stiemahardhika.ac.id

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ABSTRACT: Differences in the division of labor within the household are often one of the issues discussed. Women are considered to do more double work roles than men. This can be seen from the many activities carried out by women ranging from cooking, washing, caring for children, to working. In this study, the authors intend to find out how the pattern of division of labor, access, and control of resources, as well as daily activities of a woman and a man from a family. The focus of this research is on household assistants who work in the informal sector and double work in the Babakan Lebak Village area, Dramaga, Bogor. In addition, the factors that influence these things also want to be known by the author. The method used in this research is the qualitative method. Case studies, observations, and in-depth interviews were conducted in this study which was then analyzed using Harvard's gender approach. The results of this study indicate that women hold more multiple roles than men. The role of access has the same access between men and women. The supporting factors are economic, socio-cultural, religious, and environmental patterns.

Keywords: Economy, Gender, Division of Work, Social

1. Introduction

Sustainable Development Goals or abbreviated as SDGs are 17 goals with 169 measurable achievements and deadlines set by the United Nations as the world development agenda for the benefit of humans and planet earth. Of the 17 goals, there is one that focuses on gender equality and women's empowerment by removing gender disparities. To achieve these targets, one of them is by increasing the ability of educational institutions to manage and promote gender-oriented education to increase people's understanding of gender equality.

The current family problems are dominated by (*socio-economic problems social-economic problems*) such as divorce, conflicts between family members, poverty, domestic violence, juvenile delinquency, and others. National economic development so far has not been able to improve the welfare of the people at large. The main indicators are high inequality and poverty. Gender inequalities still occur in Indonesia, including in the labor market, namely women's access to opportunities that bring in lower-income than men's access. Women are less likely to work, and vice versa is more likely not to be employed. Women tend to get lower wages than men.

In general, there has been a partnership between the roles of men and women in daily life with a partnership stage, which varies from one family to another, from one region to another. This gender partnership is reflected in access and control of family resources,

although perfect equality has not yet been achieved. However, there is still a gender imbalance or an imbalance of a perfect gender partnership at the community level as evidenced by the lack of women in the management of economic organizations and other social organizations. The existing women's organizations are generally religious organizations and social associations. In this case, there are still obstacles to the role of women in contributing to economic activities. Not yet established the perfect balance of roles between men and women, related to the traditional patriarchal culture of society. The culture considers men as a main/primary breadwinner and women as *a secondary breadwinner*.

In the economic field, in general, the participation of women is still low, women's ability to obtain employment and business opportunities is still low, as well as access to economic resources. This is indicated by the Labor Force Participation Rate (TPAK) which is still far from men, which is 45% while men are 75.34% (Sanoessi, 2003).

Based on this description, researchers are interested in studying how the pattern of organizing gender in one of the households around the campus, where this household is a family whose wife has a domestic profession as a household assistant, especially washing workers. This family condition is also inseparable from the issue of gender equality related to the division of roles in the social and economic aspects of the household.

Based on the background that has been described, the formulation of the problems examined and analyzed in this study are:

1. What is the pattern of division of labor in the washing labor household?
2. How is the division related to access and control rights in terms of resources and benefits possessed by washing labor households?
3. What are the factors that influence social construction in society in the washing labor household environment?

Based on the formulation of the problems that have been described, the objectives to be achieved in this study are:

1. Identify the pattern of division of labor in washing labor households.
2. Identify the division related to access and control rights in terms of resources and benefits owned by washing labor households.
3. Analyze the factors that influence social construction in the community in the washing labor household environment.

Gender

Gender is the nature of women who are slowly socialized evolutionarily and biologically affect each sex is an incorrect concept. Mansour Fakih (1996) in his book states that the concept of gender is a trait that is inherent in both men and women socially and culturally constructed. For example, that woman is known to be gentle, beautiful, emotional, or motherly. While men are considered strong, rational, male, mighty. The characteristics of the traits themselves are interchangeable traits. This means that there are men who are emotional, gentle, motherly while there are also women who are strong, rational, mighty. Changes in the characteristics of the traits can occur from time to time and from one place to another.

Mansour Fakih further (1996) explained that in ancient times in a certain tribe women were stronger than men but in other times and different places men were stronger. Also,

changes can occur from class to different classes of society. In certain tribes, rural lower-class women are stronger than men. All things that can be exchanged between the nature of women and men, which can change from time to time and differ from one place to another, or different from one class to another class, that is known as the concept of gender.

In line with Mansour Fakih, William-de fries (2006) in his book entitled *Gender, not Taboo (Notes on Facilitation of Women's Groups in Jambi)* suggests that Gender is different from the notion of gender. Gender is not gender. Gender is neither female nor male. Gender only contains the different functions and social roles of men and women, which are formed by the environment in which we are. Gender is created through a long process of socio-culture in a certain scope of society so that it can differ from one place to another. For example, men who wear tattoos on the body are considered great by the Dayaks, but in other community environments such as Jews, for example, this is unacceptable.

William-de fries (2006) also added that gender also changes from time to time so that it can differ from one generation to the next. For example, in the past women who wore long pants were considered inappropriate while today it is considered good for active women.

A more concrete and more operational understanding was put forward by Nasarudin Umar (1999) in his book entitled *Arguments on Gender Equality Perspectives on the Qur'an*, which states that gender is a cultural concept used to identify differences in terms of roles, behavior, and others. between men and women who develop in a society based on social engineering. Nasarudin Umar (1999) further explained that the determination of gender roles in various social systems, most of which refer to biological or gender review. Society is always based on species differentiation between men and women. Organs that are owned by women have a role in the growth of emotional maturity and thinking. Women tend to be emotionally slow. While men who can produce in themselves the hormone testosterone makes it more aggressive and more objective.

Gender Analysis Techniques

One of the tools of gender analysis is the Harvard framework which can be used to analyze the situation of gender relations in family and society. The Harvard framework consists of three components, Overholt et al. 2 This data was obtained from the results of BPS's collaboration with the Ministry of Women's Empowerment and Child Protection 11 (1986) cited by the ILO (without the year) stating that the component is an activity profile that is the division of gender work that can be seen from the activity profile. This profile includes information about who carried out the activity, when and where the activity was carried out, how many frequencies and times were needed for the activity, and how much income was generated from the activity. The division of labor analysis is intended to identify potential development activities, the time capacity of men and women to participate in the development, the imbalance of workload between men and women, and income imbalances between men and women.

Activities in the activity profile consist of productive activities, reproductive activities, and social activities. Productive activities are activities that contribute to family income in the form of money and goods. In one research report in the field of gender and forestry, Engelhardt and Rahmina (2011) state that land clearing is carried out primarily by old and young men. Cutting down trees, burning bushes, and preparing agricultural land is

dominated by men. Sowing seeds, planting, and weeding are done by both genders, but women take a larger and more time-consuming part. The utilization of Non-Timber Forest Products (HNK) from rattan and bamboo is dominated by women who produce handicrafts and have weaving skills.

Reproductive activities and household tasks are activities that ensure the survival of humans and families, such as collecting firewood, cleaning the house, washing clothes, cooking, caring for children, and caring for the elderly and the sick are dominated by women. Men are less involved. Furthermore, social activities are activities that involve the community including religious meetings, community development, and others. Religious meetings are both attended by women and men. Women are more involved in savings and loan cooperatives, PKK, and weaving groups. Meetings related to natural resource management, for example, the Meeting on Land Use Planning, are dominated by men. Women can attend meetings but do not participate actively. In general, women are responsible for providing daily food to the family. Men are expected to obtain cash to finance expenses for schooling, health care, transportation, clothing, and household assets. Women stay at home to feed their families with produce from food agriculture, while men migrate to cities (Engelhardt and Rahmina 2011). 12 2)

Then is the access profile and access control that discusses the opportunity to use resources and their results without having the authority to make decisions on how to use and the results of these resources. Furthermore, control is the control or full authority to make decisions on the use and results of resources. Profiles of access and control (opportunities and control) of resources include information about who has opportunities and control over physical or material resources, commodity and labor market, and socio-cultural resources. Next, the opportunity and mastery profile of benefits include information about who has the opportunity and mastery of income, shared wealth, basic needs, education, prestige, and so on. This analysis is useful to identify the lack of resources that can later be overcome by development programs, the imbalance of opportunities and mastery between women and men, who benefits from the use of resources, and what potential can be used or enhanced in development programs.

Access and control can also be seen from the level of participation. Accessibility can be measured by quantitative participation, i.e. how many men and women participate in certain institutions with what position and tasks. Furthermore, control is measured by qualitative participation, namely how men and women play a role in policy decisions at the institution. This analysis is carried out at formal and informal institutions in the village. The purpose of this analysis is to show the hierarchy of authority, imbalance in decision making, participation, and reasons for women's limitations. In addition, decision-making patterns in the family can also be used to see who is responsible for what, who gets what benefits, and who can be a partner for development programs.

Finally, the influence factors for solving problems related to gender relations need to be examined factors affecting the division of labor, access and control of resources and benefits, participation in institutions, and decision making in the family. These factors can be in the form of population structure, economic conditions, political conditions, socio-cultural patterns, norm systems, legislation, education systems, environment, religion, and others.

This analysis is useful for assessing the impact, opportunities, and constraints of these factors in pursuing gender equality and empowering women.

Household Assistant

Household is one of the microscopes in a community. Households are formed when there are interactions between individuals that are close or have a high level of cohesiveness. A household is defined as a person or group of people who inhabit a physical building and have 9 physical and emotional closeness. As a socio-economic unit, according to Manig (1991) in Dharmawan (2001) households have a function, namely: 1) allocation of resources that makes it possible to satisfy household needs, 2) guarantees to various household goals, 3) production of goods and services, 4) make decisions on the use of income and consumption; 5) social and material reproduction and social security for household members.

2. Research Methods

Research This research was conducted at the Al Zam-Zam Boarding House, precisely in the Village of Babakan Lebak, Dramaga, Bogor. The choice of location is because researchers want to see and analyze female households that work in the informal sector. This location is considered to be able to answer research questions regarding gender analysis in households.

This research was conducted on September 4, 2019. Field activities were carried out using interview techniques. After the data collection activities, a report was made to explain the results of the data collection in the field.

The research on gender analysis was carried out in Babakan Lebak Village, Dramaga, Bogor. Determination of informants chosen *purposively* that meets the criteria of the household where the wife in the household has a profession in the domestic field. The approach was carried out qualitatively with in-depth interviews. The results of in-depth interviews were then analyzed using the Harvard framework consisting of the division of labor, the distribution of access rights and control rights in resources and benefits as well as the factors that influence social construction.

3. Results And Discussion

Households that were used as respondents in the gender analysis and development using the Harvard framework are Ibu Nyai's household (47 years). Ibu Nyai herself works daily as a washing laborer in the Balebak Dramaga area. While Ms. Nyai's husband, Mr. Ujang (53 years) works as a casual laborer. Ibu Nyai has three children, Wahyudin (23 years), Dwiyan (22 years), Adinda (15 years). All family members still live together in one house. Three people work in the household, namely Ujang, Ibu Nyai, and Wahyudin.

Division of Productive, Reproductive, and Social Work

Table 1 Division of Productive, Reproductive and Social Work

No	Activities for	Men	Women
1.	<u>Productive</u>		
	• Work outside the home	V	
	• Work as a washing laborer		v
2.	<u>Reproductive</u>		

No	Activities for	Men	Women
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparing Meals • Wash • Cleaning the house • Wash the motorbike • Shopping for household needs 	V	v
3.	<u>Social</u>		
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community Service every Friday • Recitation 	v	v

From the results of the field data, it can be seen that the division of productive, reproductive, and social work in Ibu Nyai's household is predominantly carried out by women. When viewed from the issue of gender disparity in development as expressed by Fakhri (2000), women tend to get double workloads and stereotypes.

In a double workload, women are seen as responsible for all domestic work (homework). The fact is that the domestic workload is more numerous and requires more time to work on. In the case of Ibu Nyai's household, besides working as a washing laborer, she also has to take care of household needs and other needs such as preparing meals, cleaning the house, etc. Likewise, Adinda, as the only daughter in the house, Adinda helps Ibu Nyai every day in taking care of the household when her mother is working or not at home. Unlike boys at home, they are only tasked with completing their own needs without taking care of other household needs.

In addition, women also often get stereotypes (*labeling*) or marking. The role of women is often assumed to be an 'additional income earner', not the main breadwinner. Other markings that often occur in women are 'women at home'. Thus, it is women who are more in charge of completing household chores than men.

Access and Control

Table 2 Access and Control in the Household of Ibu Nyai

No	Resources and Benefits of	Access		Control	
		Women	Men	Women	Men
1.	<u>Resources</u>				
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicle • Land • Home Appliances • TV • Cash 	v	v	v	vv
		v	vv		vv
		vv	v		
		v	v		
		v	v	v	v
2.	<u>Benefits</u>				
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Income • Education • Basic needs • Political needs 	v	v	v	
		v	v	v	vv
		v	v	vv	v
		v	v	v	v

From the data from the field, in Ibu Nyai's household, the access of resources between women and men is equally equal. However, in terms of resource control, men are more dominant than women. If it is related to the issue of gender disparity, this happens because most women experience marginalization and subordination. In marginalization, women are prevented from gaining power, alienating individuals or groups of people from attention, influence, and power (Microsoft Encarta Reference Library 2005). Women also experience subordination (placement in the second position). Women are often considered irrational and emotional so that they cannot lead including controlling resources. This also happened to the male Nyai male household in her household having a more dominant role on the resource control side.

On the benefits side, women and men in Ibu Nyai's household both benefit. But on the income control side, men don't get it. This happens because women are considered to be more careful in organizing income and also because of the role of women who are in direct contact with organizing household needs so that it is easier if income is controlled by women.

"Yes, if the daily income of a mother who holds it, the problem is that shopping is what regulates all mothers. Fathers and children just need to use it already provided. " N-47 years old

Social and Economic Patterns The

process of socialization makes women tend to be associated with domestic activities which are considered as "less" important activities in the development of modern society. This kind of socialization process has limited women's life choices. Something outside the kitchen, children, and household are not considered a suitable place for women. Therefore, even though Ibu Nyai has been doing productive work, she also still has to do reproductive work which ultimately leads to the phenomenon of double workload.

The work occupied by Ibu Nyai is the main profession which is the backbone of the family. Most of the family's financial income comes from the washing work that is occupied by him. This has made the phenomenon of the double workload still ongoing in Ibu Nyai's household. For the sake of supporting his family, this is the path taken by Ibu Nyai and her family so that her children can still go to school and her family can survive.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of a gender analysis using the Harvard framework on the diverse division of productive, reproductive, and social work; access and control of resources; and activities in Ibu Nyai's household can be caused by various supporting factors, including.

1. **Religion Religious.** Factors are also one of the supporters of inequality in Ibu Nyai's household. According to her belief and the surrounding environment, women are not allowed to be leaders, must take care of the household and family, and must respect the head of the family. This is quite a factor why in Ibu Nyai's household, men tend to meet their own needs without having to take care of household tasks.
2. **Environment.** The environmental conditions around Ibu Nyai's household form the division of roles and positions between men and women who have been institutionalized, either in the form of direct or indirect treatment or attitudes. As in the decision-making process, the process of access and control of a resource, where the

environment tends to involve the more dominant role of men. In patriarchal societies, men tend to be given more power over the decision-making process, control, and access to resources

Women have more reproductive activities compared to men. Mrs. Nyai is an example of our interview which proves that women have a double workload. Through Harvard gender analysis, it can be seen the differences between men and women in aspects of the division of labor, access and control of resources, and their daily activities. The data shows that the division of labor is still predominantly carried out by women, in access control getting the same, and in the activities of more women in daily work. Supporting factors are religion, and the environment.

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